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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

D3.2 Call Monitoring Report 2

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Under StandICT.eu 2026 Programme, a total of **403 eligible proposals** were submitted to the first four open calls of StandICT.eu in 2023 and 2024 for a total amount of requested funding of over **€ 3.565.596**. Applicants represented **23 EU Member States and associated countries** and covered a broad range of the priority topics of the calls. The **147 successful applicants** were funded for a cumulative total of **€ 1.322.866 in financial support**. Activities funded covered **23 different priority topics** with *Artificial Intelligence* accounting for the largest number (34 out of 81 proposals funded over Open call (OC) 1, 2, 3 and 4), followed by *Cybersecurity*.

Of the recently introduced topics, it can be noted that Digital Product Passport (DPP) and Artificial Intelligence are attracting a steady increase in the number of applications submitted (with 18 funded proposals in OC3 and OC4).

The quality of the proposals was also extremely high with the average score of proposals over the funding threshold at **8.94 out of a possible 10 points for OC1, 8.63 out of a possible 10 points for OC2, 8.17 out of a possible 10 points for OC3 and 8.07 out of a possible 10 points for OC4** with an overall average score of the funded applicants for both calls of **8.45**.

It is an undeniable fact that the open calls emphasise the **truly global reach** of the European specialists in shaping and supporting European policies, regulation and strategies within ICT standards with **over two-thirds of all funded applicants contributing to International Standards Organisations**, including ISO, ISO/IEC, IEC, ITU, IEEE, and IETF; and the remainder to ESOs (ETSI, CEN or CEN/CENELEC) or to cross-SDO collaboration.

This deliverable, D3.2 “Call Monitoring Report 2”, is released at the end of Month 19 and describes activities related to the **StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme, a series of nine open calls which will provide € 2,925,000 of EU funding earmarked to support the global reach of European ICT standardisation specialists in the European ICT Standardisation Ecosystem** through 9 Open Calls to be delivered over the lifetime of the project.

This comprises selection of the open call topics, in alignment with the [MSP Rolling Plan of ICT Standardisation](#), selection and management of the External Pool of Evaluators (EPE) which falls under the remit of Task 1.4, the outcomes of OC3 and OC4 (please refer to D3.1 for details on OC1 and OC2) and the status of OC5 which closes on the 23rd of August, as well as the fellowship monitoring activities and reporting using a results-oriented approach which will continue to show more impact as the first two batches of funded projects come to a close.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	Explanation
AUS	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab (Project Partner)
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DCU	Dublin City University (Project Financial and Administrative Coordinator)
EAG	External Advisory Group
EPE	External Pool of Evaluators
EUOS	European Observatory for ICT Standards
Trust-Grants Platform	The Trust-IT Services Grants Platform
MSP	European Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation
MSs	Member States
NSB	National Standard Bodies
OC	Open Call(s)
SDO	Standard Developing Organisations
TWG	Technical Working Group
TRUST-IT	Trust-IT Services Srl (Project Technical Coordinator)
LT	Long-term fellowship
ST	Short-term fellowship
OS	One-shot fellowship
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable, “D3.2 Call Monitoring Report 2”, submitted at Month 19 of the Project, describes the outcomes of the submissions to Open Call 3 and Open Call 4 to the StandICT.eu 2026 open calls for ICT Standardisation Experts in their respective fields, the recruitment of the external experts for the evaluation of the open calls, who come together as the External Pool of Evaluators (EPE) and the work that they have performed, as well as the selection of the priority topics for the open calls.

As a further iteration of this document is foreseen over the course of the Project (D3.4), this deliverable will be incremental in content up to the last and final call so that all of the information related to the open calls are readily available for consultation in its latest version.

1.2 Structure

The document is divided in the following sections:

- *Section 2* provides a statistical overview of the applications received and funding granted through Open Call 3 and Open Call 4 closed and evaluated at the time of writing and information on the launch of Open Call 5, closing on the 23rd of August, as well as an overview of the opening and closing dates of the calls to project end with the relevant funding assigned and allocated
- *Section 3* provides a report on the composition and management of the External Pool of Evaluators (EPE) engaged under contract by StandICT.eu, as part of Task 1.4.
- *Section 4* focuses on the applications received, providing details on the ranking and related applicants.
- *Section 5* provides information on the monitoring of the projects funded.
- *Section 6* provides conclusions and lessons learned

The StandICT.eu 2026 deliverables which are related to this document are the following:

- D6.1 Plan for communication & stakeholder engagement strategy & plan and promotion of the open call
- D3.1 Call monitoring report 1
- D3.3 Fellowship Programme interim report

2. SUMMARY OUTCOMES OF THE OPEN CALLS

2.1 Open Call Guidelines and Priority Topics

StandICT.eu will provide € 2,925,000 of crucial funding to support the participation of European standardisation specialists in key international and global SDOs. Through nine open calls this funding will enable the specialists to contribute to and help create a fully integrated European Standardisation Ecosystem, thereby strengthening Europe's position in global standardisation initiatives. In order to clarify the main steps and rules of the application process, the StandICT.eu consortium has implemented and published on Zenodo the main guidelines for applicants who are interested in applying to standICT.eu Open Calls, available [here](#). The priority topics of the StandICT.eu 2026 open Calls, which are set out in Figure 1. are closely correlated to the list of priority areas of the [European Multi-Stakeholder Platform \(MSP\) on ICT Standardisation Rolling Plan](#), currently in its 2024 edition. The macro areas of the Rolling Plan include the four main EU Policies supported by ICT Standardisation: Foundational Drivers; Key Enablers; Societal Challenges; Innovation for the Digital Single Market, and Sustainable Growth, with each topic comprising multiple sub-categories. The Rolling Plan also references new relevant legislative acts such as the Data Act, Digital Services Act (DSA), Digital Markets Act (DMA) or the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA).

- **FOUNDATIONAL DRIVERS**
 - o Data Economy
 - o Cybersecurity/Network and Information security
 - o E-Privacy
- **KEY ENABLERS**
 - o 5G and Beyond (6G)
 - o Cloud and Edge Computing
 - o Big Data & Open data
 - o IoT Internet of Things
 - o Electronic identification and trust services (including e-signature)
 - o E-infrastructure for data and computing intensive service
 - o Broadband infrastructure mapping
 - o Accessibility of ICT products and services
 - o Artificial Intelligence
 - o European Global Navigation Satellite Systems (EGNSS)
 - o Quantum Technologies
- **SOCIETAL CHALLENGES**
 - o E-Health, Healthy living and ageing
 - o Digital skills
 - o Digital learning
 - o E-Government
 - o E-call
 - o Pandemic Preparedness
 - o Safety, transparency and due process online
- o Emergency communications and public warning systems
- **INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET**
 - o E-Procurement
 - o E-Invoicing
 - o Retail payments
 - o Preservation of digital cinema
 - o FinTech & RegTech Standardisation
 - o Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies
 - o Virtual Worlds including Civerse
 - o
- **SUSTAINABLE GROWTH**
 - o Smart Grids and Smart Metering
 - o Smart and Sustainable Cities
 - o ICT Environmental impact
 - o European Electronic Toll Service (EETS)
 - o Intelligent Transport Systems
 - o Digitisation of European Industry
 - o Robotics and autonomous systems
 - o Construction building information modelling
 - o Common information sharing environment (CISE) for the EU Maritime domain
 - o Water management digitalisation
 - o Single European Sky
 - o U-Space
 - o Circular Economy including Digital Product Passport

Figure 1 - Open Call TOPICS for calls 1-4

The priority topics are continuously monitored vis-à-vis European Commission objectives to ensure that the financial resources deriving from the open calls are strategically channelled to sectors and areas where additional presence of EU Member States and Associated Countries may be needed.

2.2 Summary Outcome of OC 3

Figure 2 - open call 3 banner

OC3 opened on the 30th October 2023 and closed on the 9th of January 2024. Figure 3 below provides a breakdown of the proposals submitted by topic addressed and the SDOs to which the fellows are contributing, as well as their organisation type, while Figure 4 shows how the submitted applications fit within the MSP Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. Figure 5 shows an overview of the funded proposals by topic addressed, SDOs and organisation type.

FIGURE 3 - BREAKDOWN OF SUBMITTED PROPOSALS BY TOPIC OC3

FIGURE 4 - SUBMITTED TOPICS BY ICT STANDARDISATION ROLLING PLAN OC3

FIGURE 5 - BREAKDOWN OF PROPOSALS BY TOPIC OC3

2.3 Summary Outcome of OC 4

FIGURE 6 - OPEN CALL 4 BANNER

OC4 opened on the 12th February 2024 and closed on the 12th of April 2024. Figure 6 below provides a breakdown of the proposals submitted by topic addressed and the SDOs to which the fellows are contributing, as well as their organisation type, while Figure 7 shows an overview of the funded applications.

FIGURE 7 - BREAKDOWN OF SUBMITTED PROPOSALS BY TOPIC OC4

FIGURE 8 - BREAKDOWN OF FUNDED PROPOSALS BY TOPIC OC4

2.4 Open Calls: Timing and Funding

Table 1 below presents the financial status in terms of allocated budget for Open Calls 1, 2, 3 and 4 as well as the scheduled call timings and the projected funding for each open call which is the average amount of the remaining budget subdivided by call.

The allocated funding will be closely monitored to ensure that any remaining funding with respect to the amount projected for each call is re-allocated under the subsequent calls to project completion, ensuring that all of the Financial Support for Third Parties available is utilised while not compromising the high quality of the proposals selected.

The former is a contingency for those cases where an applicant does not fulfil their reporting obligations with StandICT.eu 2026, or otherwise does not carry out the work pursuant to award and is closely tied to the monitoring activities carried out on the fellowship as further described in Section 5.

Call n.	Opening date	Closing date	Grant type	Funded fellows	Allocated funding	Projected funding	Cumulative total
1	08/05/2023	10/07/2023	LT, ST	35	€ 331.766,00		€ 331.766,00
2	31/07/2023	09/01/2023	LT, ST	37	€ 325.918,00		€ 657.684,00
3	30/10/2023	09/01/2024	LT, ST	35	€ 322.158,00		€ 979.842,00
4	12/02/2024	12/04/2024	LT, ST	40	€ 343.024,00		€ 1.322.866,00
5	24/06/2024	23/08/2024				€ 320.426,80	€ 1.643.292,80
6	02/09/2024	1/11/2024				€ 320.426,80	€ 1.963.719,60
7	22/11/2024	21/01/2025				€ 320.426,80	€ 2.284.146,40
8	10/02/2025	11/04/2025				€ 320.426,80	€ 2.604.573,20
9	28/04/2025	27/06/2025				€ 320.426,80	€ 2.925.000,00

TABLE 1 – CALL TIMINGS, FUNDED PROPOSALS AND PROJECTED BUDGET

3. EXTERNAL POOL OF EVALUATORS

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, the evaluation of the applications received in response to the open calls is outsourced to a group of external experts in ICT standardisation who come together as the StandICT.eu External Pool of Experts, or EPE.

The EPE are also selected via an open call process to ensure an impartial, transparent and consistent review process of the applications received. The first open call for evaluators was launched on the 31st of March and closed on the 31st of May 2023 with the possibility to reopen a reserve call at a later stage in the project to compensate for retiring members, changes in or broader coverage of the priority topics. The banner for the open call for Evaluators is shown in Figure 8 below.

FIGURE 9 - FIRST OPEN CALL EPE

As underlined above, the amount of applications received in OC3 and OC4 and the retirement of some evaluators has required another round of Open Call for Evaluators¹. The latter was launched on the 29th of April, 2024 and closed on the 3rd of June, 2024. The second Open Call for Evaluators has resulted in 23 new evaluators onboarded. The banner for the second open call for Evaluators is shown in Figure 9 below.

¹ <https://www.standict.eu/standict-2026-call-evaluators>

FIGURE 10 - SECOND OPEN CALL EPE

As a consequence of the new batch of evaluators coming into the project, the StandICT.eu team has organised an internal webinar dedicated to evaluators - both old and new ones - where an overview of the evaluation process was discussed. The webinar took place on the 11th of July, 2024. After the webinar, recordings and slides were sent to all evaluators.

3.1 Composition of the EPE

131 eligible applications were received in response to the first call, of which 23 were from the precursor StandICT.eu 2023 project.

37 eligible applicants were received in response to the second call, of which 23 were selected as eligible evaluators.

The applications to the first EPE call were evaluated by three partners, blind vote from the two academic Partners DCU and Fraunhofer plus Trust-IT via the Trust-Grants Platform. The applications to the second EPE call were evaluated by three partners, blind vote from DCU, Trust-IT and AUS. The evaluation was based on information provided in the application form and proven expertise in ICT standardisation and the open call priority topics demonstrated on a supporting CV. Applicants receiving three favourable votes from the Project Partners were selected to the Pool with those achieving two votes placed on a reserve list.

A list of the current EPE is provided in Table 2. Given the public dissemination level of this deliverable, this information is limited to the number of Contract, name and surname, gender, country and the current status of the evaluator - where “on hold” means that he/she is currently unavailable for OC5 but might be available for future calls.

Contract n°	Name, Surname	Gender	Country	Status	OC Batch
01/001	Amato Paola	F	Italy	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/002	Carmona Diaz Eduardo	M	Spain	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/004	Campegiani Paolo	M	Italy	Retired	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/005	Dacal Angel	M	Spain	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/006	Nikolaou Nikolaos	M	Germany	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/007	Salis Antonio	M	Italy	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/008	Pandey Pankaj		Norway	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/009	Velasco Luis	M	Spain	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/010	Gaur Sachin		Norway	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/011	Renwick Robin	M	Ireland	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/012	Trenta Andrea	M	Italy	On hold	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/013	Pavleska Tanja	F	Slovenia	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/014	Marsal Llacuna Maria Luisa	F	Spain	On hold	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/015	Pasic Aljosa		Spain	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/016	Cenkier Grzegorz Bartłomiej	M	Poland	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/017	Cadzow Scott	M	United Kingdom	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/018	Terseglav Gaber	M	Slovenia	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/019	Phipps Simon	M	United Kingdom	On hold	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/020	Prasad Ranga Rao Venkatesha	M	The Netherlands	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/021	Badea Ana-Cornelia	F		On hold	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/022	Mrak Marta	F	United Kingdom	Retired	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/023	Yonchina Pavlina Savova	F	Bulgaria	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/024	Ziegler Wolfgang Philipp	M	Germany	On hold	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/025	Iglesias Alvarez Josué	M	Austria	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/026	Lemic Filip	M	Belgium	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/027	Milicevic Kruno	M	Croatia	Retired	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/028	Chkhaidze Nanuli	M	Georgia	On hold	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/029	Wolf Andreas	M	Germany	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/030	de la Feld Marco	M	Italy	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/031	Ruffini Sergio	M	Italy	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/032	Frascolla Valerio	M	Germany	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023

01/033	Dagiuklas Anastasios	M	United Kingdom	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/034	Roseiro Pedro	M	Portugal	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/035	Magistrelli Giorgio	M	Belgium	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/036	Pastore Serena	F	Italy	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/037	Perea Escribano Carmen	F	Spain	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/038	Aileni Raluca Maria	F	Romania	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/039	Castellanos Lopez Javier	M	Spain	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/041	Sulzer Jean Francois	M	France	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/042	Wild Fridolin	M	United Kingdom	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/043	Cotton Paul	M	Canada	On hold	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/044	Hoeckner Klaus	M	Austria	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/045	Rogers Heather Lynn	F	Spain	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/046	Kaliampakas Efthymios	F	Greece	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/047	Giribaldi Davide	M	Switzerland	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/048	Hubert Pascal	M	France	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/049	Massimo Fabio	M	Italy	On hold	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/050	Burgos Solans Daniel	M	Spain	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/051	Dhaher Omar	M	Belgium	Active evaluator	1st EPE Call - 2023
01/053	García Olaizola Igor	M	Spain	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/054	Lashley Ian	M		Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/055	Frey Sebastian	M	China	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/056	Anthopoulos Leonidas		Greece	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/057	de la Torre Cubillo Luis	M	Spain	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/058	Allard Jean-Luc	M	Belgium	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/059	Stamatios Papadakis	M	Greece	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/060	Neviana Boumbarova	F	Bulgaria	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/061	Farhan Sahito	M	France	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/062	Anto Cartolovni	M	Croatia	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/063	Salvatore Randazzo	M	Italy	Retired	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/064	Ksenija Popovic		Austria	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/065	Pedro Manuel Lopes Branco	M	Netherlands	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/066	Luis Miguel Contreras Murillo	M	Spain	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/067	Ben Bland	M	United Kingdom	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024

01/068	Bastian Koller	M	Germany	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/069	Susanne Guth-Orlowski	F	Germany	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/070	Lazaros Gkatzikis	M	Greece	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/071	Lumbardha Hasimi	M	Slovakia	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/072	David Artuñedo Guillén	M	Spain	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/073	Ibrahim Halil Kirmizi		Turkey	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/074	Juergen Heiles		Germany	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/075	Aurelio Escobar	M	Spain	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/076	Ilona Cieslik	F	Switzerland	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/077	Julian Lauten-Weiss	F	Germany	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/078	Mario Brun	M	Portugal	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024
01/079	Andreea-Raluca Leru	F	Romania	Active evaluator	2nd EPE Call - 2024

TABLE 2 – UPDATED EPE LIST

3.2 EPE Assignment and Assessment of the work performed

The EPE accepted and under contract with StandICT.eu are mapped in terms of their competency on the priority topics of the open calls to match them to the applications received, while being sure to maintain a good geographical balance and gender balance where possible.

The evaluation process for Open Calls has remained unchanged for Open Call 3 and Open Call 4: for more information about the evaluation process, please refer to D3.1, Chapter 3.

3.3 EPE Payments

The External Pool of Evaluators are paid at a daily rate of € 400, or € 50 per hour. Each evaluator is paid 30 minutes for each proposal evaluated, including interaction with the other evaluators during consensus, 20 minutes for each Rapporteur role and 20 mins for Quality Control. This equates to an overall cost of € 108.33 per proposal evaluation as shown in Table 3 below.

Overall cost of each proposal evaluated	
<i>3 Evaluations (30 mins) including consensus phase</i>	75.00 €
<i>1 Rapporteur (20 mins)</i>	16.67 €
<i>1 Quality Control (20 mins)</i>	16.67 €
Total	108.33 €

TABLE 3 – COST OF EVALUATION PER APPLICATION

A list of the payments made to the EPE for OC 3 and OC 4 is provided in Table 4 and 5 below.

Contract n°	Surname, Name	Amount
01/001	Amato	316,70 €
01/002	Carmona	350,03 €
01/004	Campegiani	225,01 €
01/005	Dacal	558,37 €
01/006	Nikolaou	441,70 €
01/007	Salis	550,05 €
01/008	Pandey	275,01 €
01/009	Velasco	183,34 €
01/011	Renwick	391,70 €
01/013	Pavleska	41,67 €
01/015	Pasic	200,00 €
01/016	Cenkier	208,34 €
01/017	Cadzow	516,71 €
01/018	Terseglav	133,34 €
01/020	Prasad	116,67 €
01/023	Yonchina	316,68 €
01/024	Ziegler	541,71 €
01/027	Milicevic	275,01 €
01/029	Wolf	316,68 €
01/030	de la Feld	475,02 €
01/031	Ruffini	275,03 €
01/032	Frascolla	225,01 €
01/033	Dagiuklas	491,70 €
01/034	Roseiro	450,02 €
01/035	Magistrelli	291,68 €
01/036	Pastore	550,04 €
01/037	Perea	291,69 €
01/038	Aileni	341,68 €
01/039	Castellanos	258,34 €
01/041	Sulzer	158,34 €
01/042	Wild	391,70 €
01/044	Hoeckner	141,67 €
01/045	Rogers	175,03 €
01/046	Kaliampakas	275,01 €
01/047	Giribaldi	258,34 €

Contract n°	Surname, Name	Amount
01/048	Hubert	208,34 €
01/049	Massimo	300,01 €
01/050	Burgos	116,67 €
01/051	Dhafer	283,36 €
Total amount paid for OC3		11.917,40 €

TABLE 3 – PAYMENTS MADE TO THE EPE FOR OC 3

Contract n°	Surname, Name	Amount
01/001	Amato	341,69 €
01/002	Carmona	316,68 €
01/004	Campegiani	250,02 €
01/005	Dacal	650,04 €
01/006	Nikolaou	633,36 €
01/007	Salis	300,01 €
01/008	Pandey	141,68 €
01/009	Velasco	225,02 €
01/011	Renwick	391,69 €
01/013	Pavleska	150,02 €
01/015	Pasic	100,00 €
01/016	Cenkier	300,02 €
01/017	Cadzow	358,35 €
01/018	Terseglav	141,68 €
01/023	Yonchina	100,01 €
01/024	Ziegler	525,03 €
01/025	Iglesias	116,68 €
01/026	Lemic	258,35 €
01/027	Milicevic	216,68 €
01/029	Wolf	558,37 €
01/030	de la Feld	716,72 €
01/031	Ruffini	133,34 €
01/032	Frascolla	133,34 €
01/033	Dagiuklas	225,01 €
01/034	Roseiro	408,36 €
01/035	Magistrelli	616,71 €
01/036	Pastore	525,02 €
01/037	Perea	366,69 €

Contract n°	Surname, Name	Amount
01/038	Aileni	366,69 €
01/041	Sulzer	325,02 €
01/042	Wild	475,02 €
01/045	Rogers	91,68 €
01/046	Kaliampakas	175,01 €
01/047	Giribaldi	341,68 €
01/048	Hubert	291,69 €
01/051	Dhafer	216,68 €
Total amount paid for OC4		11.484,04 €

TABLE 4 – PAYMENTS MADE TO THE EPE FOR OC 4

Finally, pursuant to art. 204 of the EC financial regulations (Title VII, "Experts") and Art. 287 of the Rules of Application, paragraph 5, the list of the EPE members under contract with StandICT.eu 2026 that received compensations in 2023 and 2024 is the above list which has been published on the StandICT.eu 2026 website [here](#).

4. APPLICATIONS RECEIVED AND FUNDED

An overall total of **403 eligible applications** were submitted to OC 1, OC 2, OC3 and OC4. Overall, the standard of the proposals was extremely good resulting in **a total of 147 proposals funded over the two calls for a total of € 1.322.866** in allocated funding and an average score of all funded proposals **of 8.45 out of a possible 10 marks**.

Once all applicants have been informed of the outcome of their proposal, those successful are individually contacted by DCU, the Financial and Administrative Coordinator, outlining the paperwork necessary for the finance and payment process. This paperwork is completed and retained on file at the start of activities to guarantee a smooth payment process upon completion of the activities, acceptance of the reporting required and confirmation of the budgeted figures which are mandatory for payment. Information requested is kept to a minimum of the payee and payee address, bank details and a redacted bank statement or bank fee statement, confirming the bank details provided.

In parallel, the process to align the start and end dates for the fellowships, where necessary, and kick off monitoring activities carried out by AUS and the reporting to be provided fellows via their Trust-Grants platform dashboard.

A full list of the applications received in response to OC 3 and OC 4, with proposal ID, score, and funding is provided in sub-sections 4.1-4.2 below, while details on the monitoring of each fellow, the status of their projects and their overall contributions is covered in Section 5.

4.1 Applications submitted and funded under OC 3

A full list of the eligible applications received to OC 3, including those not retained for funding, is provided in Table 5 below, in order of ranking with the proposal ID, the status of the fellowship at the time of writing, grant type and funding allocated.

Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
9,60	03-471	APR	Government/Public Services	PT	Standards for Robotics and Autonomous Systems: Knowledge, Reasoning, and AI for Multiple Robots.	LT	€ 9.970
9,57	03-497	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Advance Biometric System-on-Card standard series ISO/IEC 17839	LT	€ 8.950
9,47	03-515	APR	Academia/Research	IT	Standardizing the Quantum Internet	LT	€ 9.650
9,47	03-404	APR	SMEs	AT	Lifts and Escalators in Smart Cities	LT	€ 9.800
9,40	03-494	APR	SMEs	FR	Strengthening security and privacy of biometrics applications through standards	LT	€ 10.000
9,33	03-463	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	SE	JWG between ISO/IEC JTC1 and IEC/SyC Smart Cities on Local Digital Twins	LT	€ 9.936
9,15	03-430	APR	Academia/Research	IT	Progressing the "Competence Requirements for AI Ethicists Professionals" to the Working Draft stage	LT	€ 7.800
9,13	03-393	APR	Not for Profit Organisation	BE	Deploying standards for AI enabled Photovoltaics (AIPV)	LT	€ 9.984
9,07	03-457	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	IT	Completion of TR "Data Governance & Quality for AI in EU context" including Quality in use	LT	€ 9.350
8,97	03-474	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	SE	EUDI Wallet (eIDAS2) held personal data access control	LT	€ 10.000
8,97	03-496	APR	Academia/Research	ES	European Requirements for Biometric Products	LT	€ 10.000
8,90	03-441	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	GR	Develop an ISO Technical Report standard on innovative new &	LT	€ 10.000

² APR -Approved; NAP – Not Approved; PAY – In Payment; CLO - Closed

Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
					emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases		
8,80	03-465	APR	Academia/Research	FR	Ultra-Low Power Ambient IoT Devices in 5G-Advanced	LT	€ 10.000
8,77	03-438	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	AT	Radio regulations for IoT and DPP	LT	€ 10.000
8,74	03-392	APR	SDO/National Standard Body	BE	Standards for new on-chip Integrated Circuit Quantum Random Number Generator (ASIC QRNG) devices	LT	€ 9.984
8,74	03-399	APR	Academia/Research	IT	CrowdWireless++: Further Promoting Crowd Wireless Energy Sharing	LT	€ 9.900
8,73	03-468	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	SI	ITU-T SG13 2024	LT	€ 10.000
8,73	03-426	APR	SMEs	FR	Bridging the gap between EU R&I ecosystem and worldwide standardization on Smart Energy	LT	€ 10.000
8,70	03-408	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	AT	Accuracy and evaluation methods in the context of NLP systems	LT	€ 10.000
8,67	03-424	PAID	Academia/Research	PL	Revision of ISO/IEC 15408-1:2022	LT	€ 9.650
8,65	03-434	APR	SMEs	IT	IEEE P7018 - Requirements for trustworthiness and security of pretrained AI generative models (LLM)	LT	€ 10.000
8,64	03-450	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	ITU-T FG-TBFXG Testbeds Federations Reference Model APIs Invocations Framework & Security Framework	LT	€ 7.000
8,60	03-443	PAID	SMEs	AT	Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Post Quantum Cryptography (PQC) : An equitable analysis	LT	€ 10.000
8,50	03-488	APR	SMEs	FR	Build certification scheme for En17926 (refining ISO27701 in EU context) complying with art 42 GDPR	LT	€ 10.000
8,47	03-495	APR	SMEs	FR	Towards standards convergence for digital identity	LT	€ 10.000
8,47	03-414	APR	Academia/Research	DE	Smart Circular Economy Standards for Europe	LT	€ 6.300
8,43	03-454	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Smart Contract Auditing guidelines	LT	€ 9.100
8,37	03-421	APR	Policy/Funding Agency	GR	Developing the Strategic Business Plan for Standards Development in	LT	€ 10.000

Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
					ISO/TC307Blockchain & DLT		
8,30	03-525	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	PT	AI & Cybersecurity Standards in Education: A Collaborative approach for Safer Learning Environments	LT	€ 10.000
8,27	03-477	PAID	IT Consultancy/Development	BE	Contribution to e-identification and e-authentication at CEN/CLC/JTC 13 & ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 WG5's	ST	€ 4.950
8,26	03-483	APR	Academia/Research	FR	Adaptive Context-Based Access Management for Critical Infrastructure	LT	€ 5.034
8,23	03-453	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	PL	Digital Certificates supporting Open Finance and PSD3	LT	€ 9.900
8,20	03-449	PAID	Academia/Research	IT	Building trustworthiness for artificial intelligence	LT	€ 10.000
8,20	03-479	APR	SMEs	FR	IoT Semantic Interoperability for stress management, good health and well-being	LT	€ 5.000
8,17	03-458	APR	SMEs	ES	AI-CoE: Artificial Intelligence for Business powered by Center of Excellence. TR standard	LT	€ 9.900
8,10	432	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Towards standardisation accessibility in the metaverse	LT	€ 9.950
8,10	481	NAP	SMEs	SE	Artificial Intelligence - Guidance on addressing societal concerns and ethical considerations	LT	€ 10.000
8,10	501	NAP	SMEs	FR	Developing cybersecurity standardization for Artificial Intelligence and Internet of Things	LT	€ 10.000
8,07	397	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	IT	Contribution to Mobility Integration ISO standards and to the ISO TC 204 Advisory Group 4	LT	€ 10.000
8,07	448	NAP	SMEs	UK	Strategic Standards for Sustainable Growth (3SG) Project	LT	€ 9.314
8,00	519	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	Unified Graph Data Schema	LT	€ 9.200
8,00	437	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	ES	Dev. support for ISO/IEC/IEEE 26516 Design and development of instructional videos	LT	€ 7.547

Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
8,00	442	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	Standards for Information security management and cloud service providers	LT	€ 10.000
7,86	410	NAP	SMEs	DE	Representation of domain-specific concepts in digital twins and other technical information assets	LT	€ 9.445
7,74	395	NAP	SMEs	UK	Travel Support for June and September 2024 ETSI TC CYBER & TC SAI Meetings	ST	€ 3.320
7,73	504	NAP	SMEs	AT	Standardizing the did:keri method	LT	€ 9.600
7,73	489	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	SensorThings API version 2.0 development	LT	€ 10.000
7,70	482	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	DE	Consumer-Centric Blockchain Standards: A Holistic Approach to DLT (Jul-Dec 2024)	LT	€ 9.900
7,67	507	NAP	Academia/Research	NO	Do away with customized system integration: towards Open Command and Control for cybersecurity	LT	€ 10.000
7,67	524	NAP	SMEs	IE	Project Lead - ISO TR 24878	LT	€ 10.000
7,67	447	NAP	SMEs	UK	Time To Collision as new 5G verticals analytics in Open RAN	LT	€ 9.952
7,63	402	NAP	SMEs	DE	Application of Data Space Assets Secured and Authenticated by Meta-data Provenance Narratives	LT	€ 10.000
7,54	484	NAP	SMEs	UK	Standards for the Quantum Physical Layer	LT	€ 10.000
7,50	439	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	SE	ISO/IEC 30141 - IoT Reference Architecture Edition 2 and 3	LT	€ 9.881
7,47	467	NAP	SMEs	FR	Harmonising Architectures in Decentralised Identifier / Identity Standards at ISO/TC307	ST	€ 4.950
7,43	460	NAP	Academia/Research	FR	Low-Power Wake-up Radio in 5G-Advanced	LT	€ 10.000
7,43	478	NAP	SMEs	UK	3GPP ITU-R Ad-Hoc Convenor	LT	€ 10.000
7,43	487	NAP	SMEs	BE	Trustworthy AI expertise for EU AI Act harmonized standards	LT	€ 8.925

Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
7,30	499	NAP	Academia/Research	UK	Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity Standardisation	LT	€ 7.750
7,30	461	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	IEC 62351-90-4, Migration of cryptographic algorithms	LT	€ 9.500
7,27	407	NAP	Academia/Research	UK	Supporting CyberSecurity for Vulnerable People including those with Particular Communication Needs	LT	€ 10.000
7,24	508	NAP	Academia/Research	FI	Representation of Finland in IoE edge computing and cloud computing international standards meeting	OS	€ 2.400
7,23	403	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	ES	AI standardisation in ISO/IEC and CEN/CENELEC on Ai verification and validation	LT	€ 9.994
7,20	472	NAP	SMEs	FR	Standards for Cybersecurity Conformity Assessment	LT	€ 8.941
7,20	502	NAP	Large Enterprise	PL	Analysis and Support of Standardisation on AI in European Context	LT	€ 10.000
7,20	469	NAP	Academia/Research	IT	Iterative declarative workflows with the Common Workflow Language	LT	€ 10.000
7,17	425	NAP	SMEs	FR	The EU Path to AI: AI Trustworthiness, AI Ethics, Green & Sustainability AI, Fundamental Rights	LT	€ 9.995
7,17	394	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	Danish participation in the LDDB GQL and SQL/PGQ Implementation Working Group	LT	€ 10.000
7,15	490	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	IT	Support AI-explainability standardisation, CEN/CEN-CENELEC JTC-21 WP4	LT	€ 4.500
7,10	522	NAP	Academia/Research	FI	Representation of Finnish contributions in the Cloud Computing international standards meeting	OS	€ 3.000
7,07	398	NAP	Large Enterprise	ES	Participation in SA6 to support CAPIF Guidelines from ETSI OpenCAPIF	LT	€ 10.000
7,03	503	NAP	SMEs	FR	Managing last steps ISO/IEC 27031 revision, european experts and liaisons inputs within the project	LT	€ 10.000
7,03	411	NAP	Academia/Research	GR	Data and APIs in Smart City Platforms	LT	€ 10.000

Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
7,00	431	NAP	Large Enterprise	ES	Developing ISO technical specification for an open-code BIM standard in the industrial sector.	LT	€ 4.850
7,00	521	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Standardise AI Security Goals with sufficient detail in ISO and CEN/CENELC	LT	€ 5.500
6,97	476	NAP	Government/Public Services	SI	Enhanced Consumer protection with regulated AI Cybersecurity through Standardisation	LT	€ 1.450
6,93	491	NAP	Academia/Research	MK	Contribution to Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 JWG4	LT	€ 9.900
6,84	459	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	AT	Continued maintenance and shepherding of CBOR	LT	€ 9.800
6,80	466	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	PT	Between digital identity and privacy	LT	€ 10.000
6,80	436	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	IT	Data and software quality for artificial intelligence in support of AI Act	LT	€ 10.000
6,74	409	NAP	Large Enterprise	DK	Blockchain for Carbon Markets	LT	€ 8.800
6,73	480	NAP	Academia/Research	TR	3GPP Release 19 (5G Advanced) RAN2 Network Energy Saving	LT	€ 10.000
6,70	416	NAP	Large Enterprise	DE	Implementing the Artificial Intelligence Act's fundamental rights safeguards	ST	€ 5.000
6,67	509	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Contributions to crypto-agility from the standardization of open hardware and open silicon	LT	€ 10.000
6,60	512	NAP	Not for Profit Organisation	DE	ISCC – International Standard Content Code	LT	€ 9.837
6,60	516	NAP	SMEs	ES	Contribution to European ICT standardization strategy and redesign of the governance model for ETSI	LT	€ 10.000
6,43	413	NAP	Academia/Research	CZ	Standardization in the field of cyber security	LT	€ 10.000
6,42	419	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	LoRa Mesh Network Design and Applications	OS	€ 2.600
6,37	422	NAP	SMEs	EE	Distributed, Secure, and Interoperable Tracing for Digital Product Passport (DTRACE)	LT	€ 10.000

Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
6,37	462	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	SE	SC41/AG21 - Advisory & Sectorial Liason Group for IoT & Digital Twins within Smart Cities/Utilities	LT	€ 8.886
6,30	412	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Standarization works as AI Normative Expert (ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42, CEN/CENELEC JTC1, UNE CTN71 SC42)	OS	€ 3.000
6,20	401	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	If Machines Could Feel: AI's Journey into Empathy and Emotions	LT	€ 10.000
6,10	405	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	IETF Working Group (BoF)	LT	€ 10.000
6,10	513	NAP	SMEs	BG	Consumer Dispute Resolution Framework as a Voluntary Standard in the Mataverse	LT	€ 9.800
6,08	451	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	CEN/CENELEC standardisation for the AI Act	LT	€ 10.000
6,03	520	NAP	Academia/Research	FR	Supporting the AI Act with standards for trustworthy systems and datasets in AI and NLP	LT	€ 9.550
5,94	429	NAP	SMEs	RO	Applying cybersecurity standards for Smart Cities in a city member of OASC	LT	€ 10.000
5,76	455	NAP	Government/Public Services	NO	Work within the 3GPP SA3-LI, including document handling ahead of and during meetings.	LT	€ 6.410
5,70	440	NAP	SMEs	PT	IT governance and service management standards in ISO/IEC SC40 and digitalization processes	LT	€ 8.200
5,27	518	NAP	SMEs	DE	Fortifying AI against regulation, litigation and lobotomies	ST	€ 3.051
5,20	452	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Monitoring the correlation between regulatory requirements and the further development of standards	LT	€ 9.775
5,10	470	NAP	SMEs	IT	StandarTAI: Standardising the modeling of Trustworthy AI solutions	LT	€ 9.600
4,70	510	NAP	SMEs	FR	Supporting ISO/IEC 27031 co-editor for its revision project initiated 2020 til final publication	LT	€ 10.000
4,10	514	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	UK	Support for Chair of ETSI TC eHEALTH	LT	€ 10.000

Score	Proposal ID	Status ²	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
3,90	456	NAP	SMEs	RO	Smart Water Quality Management Solution for Sustainable Ecosystem - SEWS	LT	€ 10.000
3,03	500	NAP	SMEs	UK	Into the metaverse : Delivering the secure XSG 3D web	LT	€ 10.000
2,83	498	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	For effective and efficient standardization	LT	€ 10.000
2,70	517	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	LT	Participation, contribution to ISO/IEC SC37 WG3, development of ISO/IEC 39794-2 finger format	LT	€ 4.500

TABLE 5 – APPLICATIONS RECEIVED AND RANKED OC 3

4.2 Applications submitted and funded under OC 4

A full list of the eligible applications received to OC 4, including those not retained for funding, is provided in Table 6 below, in order of ranking with the proposal ID, the status of the fellowship at the time of writing, grant type and funding allocated

Score	Proposal ID	Status ³	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
9,30	586	APR	Academia/Research	UK	Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity Standardisation (Call 4)	LT	€ 10.000
9,23	553	APR	SMEs	UK	3GPP ITU-R Ad-Hoc Convenor	LT	€ 10.000
9,20	574	APR	SMEs	FR	Integrating architecture, interoperability, cross-cutting aspects and AI standards in data spaces	LT	€ 10.000
9,10	604	APR	SMEs	AT	Lifts and Escalators in Smart Cities	LT	€ 9.950

³ APR -Approved; NAP – Not Approved; PAY – In Payment; CLO - Closed

Score	Proposal ID	Status ³	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
9,08	623	APR	Academia/Research	IT	Enabling Interfaces: Towards the Standardization of matter-flying Transducers	LT	€ 9.550
8,97	566	APR	SMEs	FR	Contribute to the Formal Draft of EN ISO 16757-5	LT	€ 10.000
8,97	634	APR	Government/Public Services	PL	Developing ISO/IEC 29128 parts 2 and 3	ST	€ 3.150
8,94	527	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	Participation in standards development for Online Age Assurance ISO/IEEE/BSI/CEN-CENELEC	LT	€ 10.000
8,90	550	APR	Academia/Research	IT	Building trustworthiness for artificial intelligence	LT	€ 10.000
8,87	581	APR	SDO/National Standard Body	DE	Enhancing AI Standards for Consumer Protection and Compliance	LT	€ 9.900
8,78	625	APR	Academia/Research	FR	Supporting the AI Act with standards for trustworthy systems and datasets in AI and NLP	LT	€ 9.750
8,77	529	APR	Academia/Research	PL	Upgrading prEN 18037 to final stage	LT	€ 5.850
8,77	551	APR	SMEs	BE	Cybersecurity standards for AI systems in response to the EC standardisation request (AI Act)	LT	€ 10.000
8,72	597	APR	SMEs	UK	Guidelines to create a Digital Product Passport (CWA)	LT	€ 9.725
8,70	526	APR	Academia/Research	ES	ISO TC 307 Working Group 5 - Governance	LT	€ 9.885
8,67	596	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	ES	AI standardisation in ISO/IEC and CEN/CENELEC on Ai verification and validation	LT	€ 9.812
8,62	567	APR	SMEs	UK	Standardisation Working Group for Quantum Interconnect	LT	€ 10.000
8,60	589	APR	Government/Public Services	NO	Work within the 3GPP SA3-LI, including document handling ahead of and during meetings	LT	€ 5.430
8,54	545	APR	Other	FR	The EU Path to AI: AI Trustworthiness, AI Ethics, Green & Sustainability AI, Fundamental Rights	LT	€ 10.000
8,53	602	APR	SMEs	PT	AI & Cybersecurity Standards in Education II (Project Continuation)	LT	€ 9.900

Score	Proposal ID	Status ³	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
8,50	535	APR	SMEs	DE	Convenorship for AI Act Standardization Request CEN CENELEC JTC 21 WG 5 Cybersecurity	LT	€ 10.000
8,47	636	APR	SDO/National Standard Body	LT	Advance Biometric System-On-Card (ISO/IEC 17839) Standard improvement	ST	€ 5.000
8,40	560	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	AT	IoT identification standardisation	LT	€ 10.000
8,37	598	APR	Academia/Research	ES	Guidelines for the Data Management within On-Boarded European Digital Identity Wallets	LT	€ 10.000
8,37	622	APR	Academia/Research	LU	Towards Standardized End-to-End Security for the Internet of Constrained Things	ST	€ 5.000
8,37	570	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	EU Data Act - Evaluation and filling of standardisation gaps to satisfy technical provisions of it	LT	€ 8.100
8,33	543	APR	SMEs	FR	IoT Semantic Interoperability for Internet of Robotic Things	LT	€ 5.000
8,33	616	APR	SMEs	FR	Developing cybersecurity standardization for Artificial Intelligence and Internet of Things	LT	€ 10.000
8,30	612	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	Develop Amendment to extensible minutiae standard ISO/IEC 39794-2	LT	€ 6.900
8,30	558	APR	Large Enterprise	ES	Participation in SA6 to support CAPIF Guidelines from ETSI OpenCAPIF	LT	€ 10.000
8,27	603	APR	SMEs	BE	Adaptive and multiple output power supplies based on USB Type C connector and USB PD support	LT	€ 10.000
8,25	579	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	Role-based acces control for electric power systems	LT	€ 9.700
8,20	605	APR	Academia/Research	PT	Contribution to new standard for autonomous robotic systems IEEE1872.3	LT	€ 10.000
8,20	606	APR	SMEs	AT	Write a specification for a W3C VC Data Integrity suite that is compliant with JAdES	LT	€ 9.600
8,15	624	APR	SMEs	DE	Representation of domain-specific concepts in digital twins and other	LT	€ 9.960

Score	Proposal ID	Status ³	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
					technical information assets		
8,13	607	APR	Academia/Research	IL	Actively contribute to ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC38 and IEEE S2ESC to harmonize Cloud and DevOps standards	LT	€ 3.300
8,10	542	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Guidance (ISO 19770-10) for implementing IT asset management	LT	€ 10.000
8,10	614	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	IEC 62351-90-4, Migration of cryptographic algorithms	ST	€ 4.800
8,07	561	APR	SMEs	BE	Trustworthy AI and AI Risk Management expertise for EU AI Act harmonized standards	LT	€ 7.862
8,07	593	APR	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Artificial Intelligence - Operational Design Domain for AI systems	ST	€ 4.900
8,02	633	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Promoting Dataspace Standardization for Data Interoperability in the Digital Single Market	LT	€ 10.000
8,00	547	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	LoRa Mesh Network Design and Applications	OS	€ 2.600
8,00	591	NAP	SMEs	IT	Competence Framework for Artificial Intelligence	LT	€ 4.800
8,00	628	NAP	Academia/Research	PT	JPEG Exploration on NeRF representation and coding	LT	€ 10.000
7,95	608	NAP	SMEs	ES	Contribution to European ICT standardization strategy and redesign of the governance model for ETSI	LT	€ 10.000
7,90	621	NAP	Academia/Research	GR	Connectivity requirements analysis of verticals	LT	€ 10.000
7,80	580	NAP	Academia/Research	UK	Supporting Bi-directional Communication with Users (including Vulnerable End Users) of Cyber Systems	ST	€ 5.000
7,80	630	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Security Audit of Smart Contract - Technical Report	LT	€ 8.100
7,73	601	NAP	Academia/Research	AT	Closing Gaps in QKD System and QKD Network Security Assurance	LT	€ 9.800
7,70	626	NAP	SMEs	FR	Build certification scheme for En17926 (refining ISO27701 in EU context) complying with art 42 GDPR	LT	€ 10.000
7,67	592	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Standards for AI Ethicists	LT	€ 9.953

Score	Proposal ID	Status ³	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
7,50	582	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DK	Enhancing the ISO 39075 GQL standard with Knowledge Graph functionality for AI application support	LT	€ 10.000
7,50	617	NAP	SMEs	FR	Benchmarking Architectures in Decentralised Identifier / Identity Standards for ISO/TC307	ST	€ 4.950
7,45	600	NAP	SDO/National Standard Body	PT	AI standardisation: facilitating the understanding and implementation of the AI Act in Portugal	LT	€ 9.800
7,43	541	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Facilitating compliance with the AI Act's fundamental rights requirements	ST	€ 5.000
7,40	556	NAP	SMEs	UK	Application of statistical methods - Lean Six Sigma and Big Data Analytics	LT	€ 10.000
7,35	577	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	BE	Contribution to e-identification and e-authentication at CEN/CLC/JTC 13 & ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 WG5's	ST	€ 4.950
7,30	528	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Online access to age-restricted goods or services while preserving the privacy of individuals	ST	€ 6.900
7,27	613	NAP	Academia/Research	MK	Contribution to ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17 "Cards and security devices for personal identification"	LT	€ 9.900
7,27	615	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	GR	Standards development on blockchain technologies that can impact Sustainable Finance	LT	€ 10.000
7,10	587	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	FRESCEU: Framework for Aligning Ethical AI Standards Conformance with EU Policy	LT	€ 9.768
7,07	620	NAP	Other	NL	Scaling up participation in writing fundamental rights-related AI Act standards	LT	€ 10.000
7,03	632	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	BG	Industrial Data Ontology: Tooling and Ontology Contributions	LT	€ 10.000
7,00	544	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	ES	iDPP: Interoperable Digital Product Passport	LT	€ 9.900
6,97	573	NAP	Other	ES	eGov4x: eGOVERNMENT boost via ICT Standards, state-of-the-art	LT	€ 9.900

Score	Proposal ID	Status ³	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
					Technical Report (TR)		
6,97	585	NAP	SMEs	BG	Consumer Dispute Resolution Framework as a Voluntary Standard in the Metaverse	LT	€ 9.350
6,96	530	NAP	Academia/Research	UK	Improving Trustworthiness of Internet Standards	LT	€ 7.328
6,95	629	NAP	SMEs	BE	Methods for cybersecurity evaluation and testing under RED cybersecurity essential requirements	LT	€ 9.900
6,95	531	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Coordinate the International standards in the field of Techniques for Specifying IT Systems	LT	€ 7.150
6,93	554	NAP	Academia/Research	TR	Network Energy Savings	LT	€ 6.750
6,90	594	NAP	Academia/Research	IL	Enabling Participation at ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 plenary Finland	ST	€ 2.750
6,82	569	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	NO	Standardization works related to construction Data Dictionaries and Digital Product Passports	LT	€ 10.000
6,80	588	NAP	Other	DE	Fortify AI against regulation, litigation and lobotomies	OS	€ 1.200
6,75	572	NAP	Academia/Research	MT	Strengthening alignment of cybersecurity standardisation to EU priorities	LT	€ 10.000
6,70	610	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	EE	A Best Practice Guide for Developing Standards Aligned with EU AI Act	LT	€ 10.000
6,63	538	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Establishing Trust in Digital Ecosystems	LT	€ 10.000
6,60	578	NAP	Academia/Research	DE	Smart Circular Economy Standards for Europe	LT	€ 6.300
6,60	571	NAP	SMEs	UK	Promote AI trustworthiness, safety, health and fundamental rights in EU / International AI Standards	LT	€ 10.000
6,58	533	NAP	SMEs	UK	Support to Update ETSI TC HF TR 102 133: Access to ICT by young people: issues and guidelines	LT	€ 9.942
6,50	638	NAP	SMEs	FR	ReAL – Requirements for Autonomy Levels identification and disclosure	ST	€ 6.820

Score	Proposal ID	Status ³	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
6,47	627	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	BG	Semantic Support to Smart Grid Standards	LT	€ 9.980
6,45	584	NAP	SMEs	AT	Standardization of synaptic values	LT	€ 10.000
6,45	599	NAP	SMEs	BE	Participation in the standardisation work at the ESOs for the Cyber Resilience Act proposal	LT	€ 10.000
6,44	555	NAP	Academia/Research	TR	AI/ML for Mobility in 5G Advanced New Radio	ST	€ 3.600
6,30	590	NAP	Government/Public Services	SI	Enhanced Consumer protection with regulated AI Cybersecurity through Standardisation	LT	€ 1.450
6,17	557	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	DE	JTC24 DPP Framework and System Contribution	OS	€ 3.225
5,95	631	NAP	Academia/Research	FR	Evaluation of an ontology of Administrable Dose Forms for the implementation of IDMP standards	LT	€ 9.930
5,82	635	NAP	Other	SE	ETSI/CEN/CENELEC eAccessibility JTB Chair	LT	€ 9.900
5,80	552	NAP	Government/Public Services	DE	EU law enforcement participation in standardisation process	LT	€ 10.000
5,67	540	NAP	SMEs	UK	Travel Support for September and December 2024 ETSI TC CYBER & TC SAI Meetings	ST	€ 3.320
5,67	563	NAP	Academia/Research	GR	Community-Based Smart City Digital Twin Platform for Optimised DRM and Enhanced Community DisasResil	LT	€ 10.000
5,45	575	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	FR	Trustworthiness overview and concept	LT	€ 7.300
5,45	576	NAP	Other	CZ	Standardization in the field of cyber security	LT	€ 10.000
5,35	564	NAP	Academia/Research	TR	Digital skills-Oriented MOOC System	LT	€ 10.000
5,27	568	NAP	Academia/Research	ES	Standardization works as AI Normative Expert (ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42, CEN/CENELEC JTC1, UNE CTN71 SC42)	OS	€ 3.000
5,20	549	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	UK	AI startup and SME representation in project JT021008 - prEN XXX AI trustworthiness framework	LT	€ 8.170

Score	Proposal ID	Status ³	Organisation Type	Country	Proposal Title	Grant Type	Amount
4,77	595	NAP	SMEs	AT	TRIBOLOGY CHALLENGE: Harmonization of Tribological Practices in Reciprocating Tests	LT	€ 10.000
4,20	637	NAP	Academia/Research	SE	DataReadiness	LT	€ 10.000
3,60	583	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	PL	Drones for rural development	LT	€ 9.250
3,47	546	NAP	IT Consultancy/Development	EE	Strategic ICT Selection Guidebook: Enhancing Enterprise Competitiveness and Accessibility in Europe	LT	€ 10.000
2,13	537	NAP	SMEs	FR	Expertise in developing acceptability and governability around AIs based systems	ST	€ 5.600
1,00	618	NAP	SMEs	FR	Co-edition of ISO/IEC 27031 for its 2023 revision initiated in 2020	LT	€ 6.000
1,00	619	NAP	SMEs	FR	Managing ISO/IEC 27031 revision finalization, ensuring consensus with SC27 management and liaisons	LT	€ 10.000

TABLE 6 – APPLICATIONS RECEIVED AND RANKED OC 4

5. MONITORING OF THE FUNDED FELLOWS AND IMPACT

5.1 Monitoring Status of the Fellowship Programme at M19

The monitoring methodology of the Fellowship Programme is detailed in Deliverable 3.1 Call Monitoring Report 1. This deliverable gives an updated view on the current status of the fellowship programme in terms of monitoring at M19.

Open Call #1 monitoring run from September 2023 until June 2024. In this batch, a total of 35 fellowships were awarded, 17% of these fellowships are carried out by women, and 29% of the funded experts are new to the programme (i.e., they have not participated in the earlier funding batches of StandICT.eu). Moreover, 62% contribute to international standardisation organisations, including ISO, ISO/IEC, IEC, ITU, IEEE, and IETF; the remainder contributes to ESOs (ETSI, CEN or CEN/CENELEC) or to cross-SDO collaboration. This batch is closed, all fellowships have been concluded since June 2024.

Open Call #2 fellowship monitoring was launched in mid-December and is soon to be closed as the very last fellowship of this batch will finish at the end of August 2024. In total 37 fellowships were funded; with 11% of projects run by female experts. Five experts of this group are new to the programme, others are returning fellows. 62% of the fellows' activity contribute to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs, including IEC, IEEE, IETF, ISO, ISO/IEC and ITU, while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC.

Open Call #3 monitoring was started in March 2024 and it will be running until April 2024. This batch funded a total of 35 fellowships out of which 23% were conducted by women experts. 34% of the funded experts are new to the StandICT.eu programme, and the reminder are returning fellows. 66% of the fellows' activity contribute to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs, including IEC, IEEE, IETF, ISO, ISO/IEC and ITU, while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC.

As shown in Figures 10 and 11, the interim report collection is almost finished (only three interim reports pending in this batch), and the final report collection is almost on its half-way.

FIGURE 11 - OC3 MONITORING STATUS INTERIM REPORTS

FIGURE 12 - OC3 MONITORING STATUS FINAL REPORTS

Open Call #4 monitoring was started in June 2024 and will end in September 2025. In this batch, 40 fellows were funded with 25% of engaged female experts. 30% of the funded experts are new to the programme, and the remainder are returning fellows. 65% of the funded activities contribute to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs including ISO/IEC, IEEE, IETF, ISO 3GPP, W3C ERCIM, and IEC while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC.

As shown in Figures 12 and 13, the report collection under this batch is in its starting blocks and will pursue in the coming months.

FIGURE 13 - OC4 MONITORING STATUS INTERIM REPORTS

FIGURE 14 - OC4 MONITORING STATUS - FINAL REPORTS

6. NEXT STEPS

Open Call 3 and Open Call 4 have been characterised by an increase in the number of applications, together with an increase in the number of funded applications which has been evident in particular with Open Call 4.

Due to the increased number of applicants, the workflow surrounding open calls has been updated and some modifications to the Trust-Grants Platform have been implemented, in order to smooth the evaluation process. In addition to this, StandICT.eu has also recruited new evaluators between April and June 2024.

Given that Open Call 5 will close in August 2024, the new batch of evaluators selected in June will be admitted to the evaluation process of OC 5.

In terms of monitoring the funded fellowships, the monitoring of the Open Call Batches #3 onwards will continue, with Open Call 5 Batch monitoring to be kicked off in October 2024.

Funded fellows are now also available on StandICT.eu website, with a dedicated section [here](#).

In terms of impact assessment, the project continues to demonstrate the concrete results of the funded fellowships via its Open Call impact report series⁴ that has been updated with three new releases. These reports showcase the funded activities and achievements of the fellowships under each funding batch. The next impact report, dedicated to Open Call 4 will be published in October 2024.

⁴ <https://www.standict.eu/2026-impact-report>